

characteristic ring vibrations of the heterocyclic bases in the range 1 600–450 cm⁻¹ generally show significant changes on complexation⁶ which could not be distinguished because of mixing or overlapping with C=O stretching bands. However, the band obtained at 970 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of pyridines shifted to ≈ 990 cm⁻¹ with a gain of intensity in the spectra of their complexes. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes observed at ≈ 500 and ≈ 700 cm⁻¹, respectively, are shifted to higher frequencies in mixed ligand complexes indicating their coordination through nitrogen.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies: All complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} are diamagnetic indicating their square-planar structure while Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic with one unpaired electron. In the case of Cu^{II} complexes three bands at 15 500, 19 500 and 22 000 cm⁻¹ are obtained corresponding to the transitions, ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and charge-transfer, respectively, which indicate their square-planar stereochemistry⁷. In the case of diamagnetic complexes of d⁸ metal ions, three spin-allowed d-d transitions are anticipated corresponding to the transitions from three lower lying d-orbitals to the empty d_{x²-y²} orbital and the charge transfer bands of lowest energy are expected to involve transitions from the highest filled metal orbitals to the most stable empty ligand, molecular orbital, the a_{2u}(π*). Pd^{II} complexes gave bands at 23 000, 29 300 and 31 500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g, respectively, and one charge transfer band corresponding to the transition a_{1g}(σ*) → a_{2u}(π*) (¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}). Three charge transfer bands at 36 000, 39 500 and 41 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1u}, π* → a_{2u}(π*), i.e. ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_u and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}, respectively, were obtained in the case of Pt^{II} complexes. The last two transitions were from the molecular orbitals localised on the ligands to molecular orbitals localised on the metal and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_u transition was more intense than ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u} transition.

The three orbital parameters Δ₁, Δ₂ and Δ₃ for Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes were calculated⁸ using the orbital and inter-electronic repulsion energies of excited states for d⁸ square-planar complexes (Table 2) for comparison. The separation Δ₁ was the largest which indicated that d_{x²-y²} was much

more strongly antibonded than any of the other d-orbitals. The separation Δ₃ for Pt^{II} complexes was less than for Pd^{II} complexes which indicated that d_{xy} was much more unstable than d_{xz}, d_{yz} in the complexes of Pd^{II} and d_{xy} was much more stable than d_{xz}, d_{yz} in the complexes of Pt^{II}.

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Dioxouranium(II) with Thiophene-2-aldehydenicotinic Acid Hydrazone

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METAL complexes of heterocyclic acids and their derivatives, are known for their biological applications. Thus, CNS action of *N,N'*-diethylnicotinamide¹ and antiinflammatory² and antiulcer³ properties of Cu^{II} complexes of heterocyclic carboxylic compounds have been investigated. Studies on metal complexes of nicotinic acid and related ligands have been reported^{4,5}.

The present paper describes the synthesis of complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO₂^{II} with a new bidentate ligand thiophene-2-aldehydenicotinic acid hydrazone (TANAH) which undergoes enolisation in solution prior to complex formation (structures I and II).

TABLE 2—METAL d-ORBITAL ENERGIES FOR Pd^{II} AND Pt^{II} COMPLEXES

Orbital energy differences (cm ⁻¹) for F ₂ - 10F ₄ = 700 cm ⁻¹			
Compd.*	Δ ₁	Δ ₂	Δ ₃
[Pd(DA)(A)] and [Pd(DA)(B) ₂]	25 450	7 700	1 850
[Pt(DA)(A)] and [Pt(DA)(B) ₂]	-	12 000	-3 250

*A = 2-Aminopyridine; B = quinoline, pyridine, 2-picoline.

(I)

(II)

Experimental

Thiophene-2-aldehyde (Fluka) and nicotinic acid hydrazide (AnalaR) were used to synthesise TANAH. The metal acetates and solvents were of AnalaR grade.

Synthesis of TANAH: 0.05 M nicotinic acid hydrazide in hot ethanol (150 cm³) was slowly reacted with 0.05 M thiophene-2-aldehyde in ethanol (30 cm³) under reflux for 1 h. The white crystalline solid, obtained on cooling, was recrystallised and the purity was checked by tlc, elemental analysis and determining m.p. of successive crops of crystallisation. TANAH, thus obtained (yield 80%), was found soluble in hot ethanol, DMF and DMSO.

Synthesis of metal complexes with TANAH: 0.004 M TANAH in hot ethanol was gradually added to 0.002 M of Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or UO₂²⁺ acetate with constant stirring and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for ~ 2 h. The coloured solid that formed was filtered, washed repeatedly with ethanol and finally with ether and air-dried. The complexes were air-stable, powdery coloured solids insoluble in organic solvents.

Analytical data: C, H and N were determined by microanalytical methods. The metal content of the complexes were determined by decomposing the complexes in fuming nitric acid followed by titrimetric estimation of the metal by EDTA. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded (4 000–200 cm⁻¹) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating infrared spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra were obtained (220–1 000 nm) in solid state on a Carl-Zeiss sVSU-22 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy's method at room temperature (~ 30°). Thermogravimetric measurements were done by heating the complexes upto 800° in air at the rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of TANAH and its metal complexes (Table 1) indicate that the complexes

have the formula ML₂.2H₂O, where M is Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or UO₂²⁺ and L stands for C₁₁H₈N₂OS

The ir spectra of TANAH show characteristic bands at 3 200 cm⁻¹ assigned to N—H stretching vibration. Bands at 1 640, 1 540, 1 290, 720, 660 and 600 cm⁻¹ are attributable to $\nu_{C=O}$, ($\nu_{C=N} + \delta_{N-H}$), δ_{N-H} , δ_{C-O} in-plane, and $\delta_{C=O}$ out-of-plane, respectively^{6,7}. The evidence shows that the ligand exists in the keto form in solid state. Absence of all the above bands in the ir spectra of the metal complexes indicates enolisation of TANAH prior to complex formation with metal ions. Appearance of new bands in the complexes at ~1 585 cm⁻¹ (C=N—N=C)⁸ also indicates enolisation of the ligand.

Coordination of the metal through azomethine nitrogen is indicated by a negative shift of ~25 cm⁻¹ in the $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 630 cm⁻¹) and a positive shift of ~20 cm⁻¹ in the N—N stretching frequency (1 030 cm⁻¹) of the ligand⁹. New bands at about 530 and 455 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} , respectively^{10,11}, suggest the possible involvement of enolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen in complexation. Association of water molecules in the complexes is indicated by the appearance of bands in the regions 3 475–455, 1 665–655 and 845–35 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 12, 13).

The magnetic moment values (Table 2) of the Co²⁺ complex (μ_{eff} 4.91 B.M.) corresponding to three unpaired electrons suggests octahedral geometry^{14,15}. The electronic spectra show two d-d transition bands at 980 and 440 nm corresponding to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, favouring octahedral geometry¹⁵ around the metal ion. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio of 2.13 confirms¹⁶ the octahedral geometry of the Co²⁺-TANAH complex. The 10Dq values of the complex correspond to a weak ligand field. Energy calculations for high-spin and low-spin octahedral symmetry point out to the high-spin nature of the complex. The μ_{eff} value

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF TANAH AND ITS COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C): Start/ (Complete)	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)	
			Metal	N
C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS*	White	236**	—	18.25 (18.18)
Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown	360 (600)	10.52 (10.61)	15.24 (15.13)
Ni(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark green	360 (560)	10.54 (10.58)	15.32 (15.14)
Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown	280 (600)	11.14 (11.35)	15.15 (15.01)
Zn(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	320 (600)	11.38 (11.64)	14.94 (14.96)
Cd(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	White	320 (720)	18.36 (18.47)	13.98 (13.80)
UO ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ OS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Orange	280 (720)	35.12 (35.24)	10.99 (10.95)

*Analysis, Found: C, 57.10; H, 3.95. Calcd.: C, 57.14; H, 3.89. **M. p.

(2.98 B.M.) of the Ni^{2+} complex corresponds to an octahedral geometry having two unpaired electrons in the e_g level¹⁶. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the complex give three bands at 920, 570 and 340 nm corresponding to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, as expected¹⁷ for octahedral Ni^{2+} ion which is further confirmed¹⁷ by ν_2/ν_1 ratio of 1.62. The 10Dq value of the complex indicates that TANAH produces a weak field. The Cu^{2+} complex has a magnetic moment of 1.96 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron¹⁸. Two bands at 820 and 760 nm corresponding to the transitions, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, in the diffuse reflectance spectra, point out to the distorted octahedral geometry¹⁸ of the complex. Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} complexes are diamagnetic.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF TANAH (LH) COMPLEXES

Compd.	μ_{eff} B.M.	10Dq cm^{-1}	ν_2/ν_1	B' cm^{-1}	β	β°
$\text{CoL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.91	11 530	2.13	924	0.951	4.84
$\text{NiL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.98	10 870	1.62	963	0.912	8.78
$\text{CuL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.96	12 840	—	—	—	—

Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} complexes are diamagnetic.

Thermogravimetry: Loss of two moles of water per mole of the complexes in the temperature range 160–320° suggests that they are present in the coordination sphere of the metal ion^{19,20}. The complexes are thermally unstable at 280–360° and complete decomposition to metal oxides occurs at 560–720°.

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Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Catechol and Pyrogallol

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THE complex forming tendencies of catechol and pyrogallol have been reported earlier¹⁻³. A survey of the literature revealed that no effort appeared to have been made on the determination of the thermodynamic stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of the complexes formed by Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with catechol and pyrogallol. The present work deals with the potentiometric determination of thermodynamic stability constants and related thermodynamic parameters.

Experimental

The solutions of the metal sulphates (AnalaR) $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, catechol and pyrogallol were prepared in conductivity water. The solutions of the metal sulphates were standardised by known methods. Ferrous sulphate solution was freshly prepared for each set of titration to avoid the possibility of hydrolysis. A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly was used to measure the pH. The instrument was calibrated using buffers of pH 4.0 and 9.2.

The titrations were carried out in a specially designed double-walled beaker (250 ml, pyrex) using Calvin-Bjerrum^{9,10} titration technique as modified